

A MODELLING APPROACH FOR PREDICTING RESIDUAL STRESSES AND DISTORTIONS IN POLYMER COMPOSITES

S.J. Lord & L.G. Stringer
QinetiQ

Cody Technology Park, Ively Road, Farnborough, Hampshire GU14 0LX, UK
sjlord@QinetiQ.com

SUMMARY

A predictive tool has been developed which uses a multi-scale modelling approach, which starts from the fundamental resin chemistry and proceeds to structural finite element analysis, to predict the residual stresses and distortions in the manufacture of fibre-reinforced composite components. This paper describes the development of the modelling tool and discusses its experimental validation.

Keywords: Residual stresses, distortions, cure kinetics, Group Interaction Modelling

INTRODUCTION

High dimensional variability is inherent in the manufacture of fibre-reinforced composite components. In the aerospace industry, this stems largely from the elevated temperatures needed to process the composite materials, which give rise to residual, or frozen-in, stresses; these are exacerbated by chemical shrinkage of the resin during cure. These stresses can subsequently cause distortion and, in some instances, premature cracking of the moulding, which can only be relieved by expensive reworking and can, in severe cases, result in the structure being scrapped. The work has been aimed to develop reliable and accurate modelling tools to predict distortions in moulded components, ultimately allowing mould tools to be manufactured and curing regimes to be applied, which take these distortions into account. This will therefore result in lower cost and waste generation through 'right-first-time' manufacture.

Over the years, several publications have been concerned with the modelling of process induced stresses during the fabrication of composite structures [1-6]. Acquiring the necessary input parameters, describing the build-up of composite properties as the resin cure progresses, is challenging as experimental measurement of these properties on partially cured resins is difficult. The residual stress modelling approach described here is able to predict these essential properties from knowledge of the basic chemistry of the resin. This paper describes the methodology which has been transcribed into a predictive tool for use with Finite Element Modelling (FEM). Experimental validation of this modelling methodology is described and the results are compared and discussed.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology uses a multi-scale modelling approach which starts from the fundamental resin chemistry and proceeds to structural finite element analysis of a generic component. The composite material described here was a Hexcel 8552 epoxy/AS4 carbon fibre prepreg system, which is commonly used in aerospace composite structures. It was necessary to understand quantitatively the cure kinetics of the 8552 resin, to simulate the observed kinetics using the DryAdd method [7], and to provide a detailed description of the composition (cross-linked polymers, monomers, etc) of the resin through cure. These composition details were used in the technique of Group Interaction Modelling (GIM) [8,9] to predict the physical properties of the resin for subsequent use in engineering simulations of stress and dimensional changes in a manufactured component through cure.

An intermediate stage involved developing simulations to predict orthotropic properties of AS4 fibres in 8552 resin during the cure cycle as functions of temperature and degree of cure (DOC). A more detailed description of these methods has been presented elsewhere [10]. The cure kinetics, GIM and the orthotropic material predictions were all incorporated into user routines for the commercial finite element code ABAQUS [11]. The overall methodology, illustrated in Figure 1, can predict residual stresses and distortion of a 3D composite component during and after cure.

Figure 1 Multi-scale modelling approach for residual stress prediction.

Stress-strain model details

From the mechanisms of cure kinematics and chemical reaction, the change in resin degree of cure with time was obtained experimentally and used in the stress-strain sub-model. The degree of cure and temperature information was used in the sub-model to calculate the changing ply properties, and hence the strains caused by thermal expansion and cure shrinkage.

User subroutines UMAT and UEXPAN in ABAQUS [11] were used to implement the material model of the composite. UMAT was used to calculate the stress as a function

of time/temperature and the changing material matrix. UEXPAN was used to calculate the thermal expansion and cure shrinkage of the resin.

Examples of how the predicted DOC and resin tensile modulus may change during the cure cycle are shown in the plots in Figure 2 for two typical temperature cycles.

Figure 2 Example of DOC and resin modulus variation for different cure cycles

EXPERIMENTS

To validate the methodologies and software, the technique was applied to three U-Channel components manufactured at the University of Bristol (UoB), referenced here as channels #0, #1 and #2. An aluminium U-channel tool was prepared and manufactured by UoB. The cross section of the tool is shown in Figure 3, noting that the two corners of the channel have different radii (R30mm and R16mm). The composite components were fabricated using this tool at UoB, all having a length of 500mm and nominal thickness of 4mm. Details of the lay-ups, ply thicknesses and arm heights for each component are given in Table 1, noting that UoB #1 and UoB #2 are essentially the same.

Table 1 Summary of main differences for the U-channel components

U-channel name	Ply thickness (mm)	Lay-up	Length (mm)	R16 arm height (mm)	R30 arm height (mm)
UoB #0	0.25	[45/90/-45/0/45/0/-45/0] _s	500	60	46
UoB #1	0.125	[-45/90/45/0/-45/0/45/0/0/45/0/-45/0/45/90/-45] _s	500	75	65
UoB #2	0.125	[-45/90/45/0/-45/0/45/0/0/45/0/-45/0/45/90/-45] _s	500	75	65

All components were manufactured using the epoxy prepreg system of Hexcel 8552 resin and AS4 unidirectional fibres. The temperature cycle for the autoclave cure process of these components was the Cycle-1 profile as shown in Figure 2. During each cure process, an autoclave pressure of 6.9 bar was applied on the surface of the

composite. When the pressure was released at the end of the process, each formed component was removed from the tool surface and the shape of the component was measured (for comparison against the predictions from FE models).

Figure 3 Cross section of U-Channel tool

After manufacture, each component was measured in terms of spring-in of the arms. The definition of the spring angles is as follow. Referring to Figure 4 for the nomenclature, the angles ϕ_{R16} and ϕ_{R30} were calculated by taking coordinates along each arm and the base and calculating the slopes m_{Ri} (where i is 16 or 30) and m_{BASE} :

$$\phi_{Ri} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{m_{Ri} - m_{BASE}}{1 + m_{Ri} m_{BASE}} \right)$$

Figure 4 Measurement and definition of spring-in for a U-Channel component

A positive angle is measured anti-clockwise, and a negative angle is measured clockwise, from the tangent m_{BASE} . The spring-angles ϕ_{S16} and ϕ_{S30} (which are also

directional) are then defined as $\phi_{Si} = \phi_{Ri} - k_i(90^\circ + k_i \phi_{Di})$, where $k_i = \frac{\phi_{Ri}}{|\phi_{Ri}|}$ and ϕ_{Di} is the draft angle of the tool. As seen in Figure 3, the draft angle was 2° on each side; again this has to be defined as directional, so here $\phi_{D16} = 2^\circ$ and $\phi_{D30} = -2^\circ$. However, the spring-angles calculated in this paper have all been “spring-in” and all of the angles have been made positive.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The channel was modelled using both the option of continuum solid or laminate solid elements and the tool was modelled as a rigid surface, as shown in Figure 5. For U-Channel #0, two FE models were considered: one with laminated solid elements with 4 elements through the thickness, each element containing 4 plies, and the other with solid elements with 16 layers through the thickness (one element per ply).

The other channels (#1/#2) were also modelled using two FE models: one with laminated solid elements with 4 elements through the thickness, with each element containing 8 plies, and the other with solid elements with 32 layers through the thickness (one element per ply).

In the FE analysis, to avoid numerical problems, pressure and gravity were applied on the composite through part of the cure cycle, once the resin modulus became significant. During the cycle, the material properties evolved and strains due to thermal expansion were built up. At the end of the process, the pressure was released and the spring-in of the component from the tool was calculated at various points along the length, as defined in Figure 4.

Figure 5 FE mesh models for U-Channel tool and component

Importance of modelling full cure cycle

An inherent computational difficulty with this type of modelling work is dealing with materials which have very small stiffness values, i.e. the resin prior to gel. It is tempting to model the process from the gel point when the resin starts to build up some stiffness, since prior to that the resin material properties do not change significantly. This is demonstrated in Figure 2 where the change in resin modulus is shown against the cure process time.

However, in starting the analysis from the gel point, the expansion and cure shrinkage accumulated in the fibre and the resin up to the gel point would be ignored. This is an important aspect which must be considered in attempting to predict distortion of cured components. This is illustrated in Figure 6, where predicted spring-in angle of a U-channel is shown for a full cure and a cure from the gel point and beyond. It clearly shows that there is a difference in the predictions, with smaller spring-in angles predicted by the part-cure process.

To model the full cure process, and to handle low moduli material, it was necessary to carry out the analysis in two steps; before and after the gel point. Before the gel point, all degrees of freedom of the nodes were fixed so that the analysis could be carried out even though the resin had little stiffness otherwise the numerical difficulties described above would have resulted. During this step, the stiffness of the resin built up and a tension was generated inside the component because of thermal expansion and cure shrinkage. After the gel point, the extra constraints were released to model the remaining cure process. The inclusion of the effect of thermal expansion before the gel point leads to larger spring-in angles being predicted (which tended to be in better agreement with those obtained experimentally).

Figure 6 Comparison of full- and part-cure results

COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENT

The spring-in angles from FE predictions and experimental measurements for U-channel #0 are shown Figure 7. It can be seen that the spring angles predicted by the FE model are higher than those measured from experiments, with the model with elements through the thickness being most representative.

Figure 7 Spring-in angles of U-Channel #0

Figure 8 shows the spring-in angles from FE predictions and experimental results from U-channels #1 and #2. Firstly, it is seen that the spring angles from the two experiments are in good agreement with each other but differ from the results obtained from U-channel #0; Figure 7. The predicted results show improvement as the number of elements through the thickness was increased; the 32 layer solid model shows very good agreement with the experiments.

Figure 8 Spring-in angles of U-Channels #1 & #2

DISCUSSION

Experiments

The three manufactured U-channels of a similar specification lend themselves to further comparisons here. Table 1 shows the main difference between the three components, while Figure 9 shows the differences in the measured spring-in between the three components, for both the R16 and R30 arms.

Figure 9 Comparison U-channel experimental spring-ins

The spring-in measurements of the R16 side showed little variability along the length for each U-channel. The level of spring-in for the three UoB U-channel specimens varied from 0.8° to 1.0°, with the UoB #1 and UoB #2 U-channels being within less than 0.1° of each other, with an average spring-in of 0.94°.

For the R30 side, the variation along the length of the spring-in measurements showed a variability of nearly 0.2° for the UoB #0 U-channel measurements. In this data set for the R30 side, there was a range of around 0.4° for the levels of spring-in measured. Again the UoB #1 and UoB #2 U-channels showed to be a better data set with variations in levels of less than 0.1°, with an average spring-in of 0.93°.

Therefore, taking the UoB #1 and UoB #2 U-channels as the more reliable data sets there appears to be little difference in the amount of spring-in between the R16 and R30 sides.

Although similar, these components did differ in some respects. It is these variables which may account for the differences seen in the figures, although it must be expected that some level of measurement error is inherent in these results, considering the difficulty in manufacturing reproducibly and in making experimental measurements on small angles to this degree of accuracy.

Modelling

The spring-in angles of the example trial components were typically of the order of 1° . With such small distortions, albeit unwanted in the final component, as mentioned above, there are inherent difficulties in making these measurements, thus leading to errors in the experimental data. However, the available data has been compared to the predicted results; the average percentage differences are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Average percentage deviations of predicted and experimental values

Component \ Location	Model	% difference	
		R16	R30
U-channel #0 (UoB)	4 elements x 4 plies	-22%	-38%
	16 elements x 1 ply	-6%	-24%
U-channel #1 (UoB)	4 elements x 8 plies	-14.5%	-18%
	32 elements x 1 ply	-4.5%	-8.5%
U-channel #2 (UoB)	4 elements x 8 plies	-11.5%	-14.5%
	32 elements x 1 ply	-2%	-5%

From the calculations shown in Table 2, for U-channel #0 it is seen that the more accurate model is indeed the one with the finer mesh (16 elements through the thickness). A similar trend was seen for U-channels #1 and #2 where the more accurate model (less than 10% difference) has the finer through-thickness mesh.

Figure 10 Comparison of solid FE spring-in results for U-channels with 0.25mm plies and 0.125mm plies

Also of interest to note are the apparent differences between the FE results for the U-channel solid models made from 0.25mm thick plies and 0.125mm thick plies (with respectively 16 elements and 32 elements through the thickness), as seen in Figure 10. Although the models have the same overall thickness of 4mm and both (balanced) lay-ups have the same percentage of the different ply orientations, the lay-ups were not

identical (in that the order of the plies were slightly different), and also the arm lengths were modelled as in the experiments (see Table 1); this may have contributed towards the difference in the results. However, given that this has been noted, the overall variability between the results was about 0.1°.

For all the cases, the finer model produced more accurate results; this was most likely due to the fact the greater number of layers of elements through the thickness allows more deforming flexibility.

CONCLUSIONS

A methodology has been developed to predict residual stresses and distortion of 3D composite components. The method has been developed from the basics of resin cure kinetics and how chemical composition changes with time and temperature to give lamina material properties during cure.

The methodology has been transcribed into a software tool, which currently resides as user subroutines in the finite element code ABAQUS.

In using the software tool, it is important to model the full cure process since the expansion and cure shrinkage developed prior to the resin gel point significantly contributes to the final distortions.

The models show greater accuracy with a greater number of elements through the thickness of the laminate; this may be varied at different parts of the structure; for example, more elements in highly curved areas.

The predicted results from the model have been compared to results from manufactured test pieces. For most cases considered, using the finer meshes, the results are in good agreement with differences of 15% or less. When a model with a larger number of elements through the thickness is used, the prediction was very close to that actually measured (2.5-5%).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of The Defence Technology & Innovation Centre (DTIC) in funding this work. Many thanks to David Porter for his input to the work on the GIM and DryAdd modelling. Also thanks to Prof. Wisnom and colleagues of the University of Bristol for their part in the research of this work.

REFERENCES

1. White, R. & Hahn, H.T. "Process Modeling of Composite Materials: Residual Stress, Development during Cure. Part I. Model Formulation", *Journal of Composite Materials*, **26, 16**, 2402-2422 (1992).
2. Jain L.K. & Mai Y.W. "On residual stress induced distortions during fabrication of composite shells", CRC-AS EP95005, Co-operative Research Centre for Aerospace Structures (July 1995).

3. Johnston, A. *An integrated model of the development of process-induced deformation in autoclave processing of composites structures*, Ph.D. thesis, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver (1997).
4. Johnston, A., Vaziri, R. & Poursartip, A. “A plane strain model for process-induced deformation of laminated composite structures”, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **35(16)**, 1435-1469 (2001).
5. Nelson, R.H. & Cairns, D.S. “Prediction of Dimensional Changes in Composite Laminates During Cure”, *34th International SAMPE Symposium*, 2397-2410 (May 1989).
6. Radford, D.W. & Rennick, T.S. “Separating Sources of Manufacturing Distortion in Laminated Composites”, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **19**, 621-641 (2000).
7. DryAdd Software Manual, Oxford Materials Ltd.: see www.oxmat.co.uk
8. Porter, D. *Group interaction modelling of polymer properties*. New York, Marcel Dekker (1995).
9. Porter D, “Materials modelling: A bridge from atoms to bulk properties”, *Advanced Performance Materials*, **3**, 309-324 (Jul 1996).
10. Stringer, L.G. “A chemistry to structures approach to modelling of residual stresses and dimensional distortion in composite parts”. 14th SICOMP Conference on Manufacture and Design of Composites, June 17-18 2003, Sweden.
11. ABAQUS User Manual version 6.7 (2007).